

FLEXBIT PROJECT

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Deliverable 1.1 – FlexBIT Architecture Blueprint

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FlexBIT Consortium

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the extended version of the **FlexBIT Architecture Blueprint**, defining the conceptual, functional, and technical framework of the FlexBIT platform. The architecture establishes how distributed energy resources (DERs), IoT systems, SCADA environments, analytics modules, and market interfaces interact within a secure, scalable, and interoperable ecosystem.

The updated blueprint serves as a foundation for technical implementation in WP2, WP3, and WP4, supporting real-world validation across all demonstrators (Germany, Italy, Poland, Grece, Malta).

2 Objectives and Scope

The main objective of D1.1 “FlexBit architecture Blueprint” is to define the FlexBIT architectural framework that ensures system interoperability, scalability, and security across all demonstrators (Germany, Italy, Poland, Greece, Malta). The scope covers both the functional and technical aspects of the system, from energy data acquisition to analytics and business logic.

2.1 Specific goals include

- Defining the main architectural layers and their interactions.
- Assigning partner responsibilities within the system.
- Describe the data exchange and communication framework.
- Establishing the technological foundation for FlexBIT deployment.
- Providing interoperability guidelines and security measures.

2.2 Additional Focus Areas

- Include detailed energy system communication protocols.
- Introduce data flow and use-case diagrams.
- Provide guidelines for scalability, failover, and container orchestration.

3 Energy Systems Integration

3.1 Integration Diagram

Figure 1 FlexBIT System Architecture Overview

The **FlexBIT architecture** is a modular, layered system designed to integrate physical and digital assets for flexible energy management. It enables real-time data exchange, control, and optimization of distributed resources across all demonstrators.

3.2 Integration Concept: Local Autonomy and Central Coordination

The FlexBIT architecture follows a **two-loop control concept** to balance local autonomy with system-wide coordination:

1. **Fast Control Loop (Local Autonomy)**

Each demonstrator operates autonomously through its **pilot-specific control systems** (e.g., SCADA, PLC, or EMS).

These local systems manage real-time operations — such as inverter control, BESS charge/discharge cycles, and safety responses — within milliseconds to seconds.

This loop ensures operational reliability and responsiveness without dependency on external communication.

2. **Slow (Advisory) Loop – FlexBIT Coordination**

FlexBIT collects aggregated operational and contextual data from each demonstrator via **MQTT, OpenAPI, or RESTful interfaces**.

Based on predictive analytics and flexibility optimization algorithms, FlexBIT provides **advisory signals**

back to the demonstrators — for example, recommending when to export energy to the grid or prioritize self-consumption.
 This advisory control operates on a slower timescale (minutes to hours) and does not interfere with the local safety or real-time operation of each pilot.

Communication between both layers is secured via **VPN tunnels** and **TLS-encrypted MQTT or HTTPS connections**, ensuring data integrity and confidentiality.

The architecture thus enables **distributed intelligence**, where demonstrators retain control of sovereignty, while FlexBIT acts as a **decision-support and coordination layer** for overall system optimization.

Figure 2 slow and fast control loop

3.3 Communication Protocols

Protocol	Layer	Application	Description
Modbus TCP	Field/Control	Solar inverters, battery controllers	Standard for monitoring and control of DER devices
IEC 61850	Control/SCADA	Wind turbines, substations	Enables standardized communication between IEDs and SCADA systems
OPC UA	SCADA/Data Acquisition	Cross-system interoperability	Secure, platform-independent industrial communication
MQTT	Data Transport	IoT gateways, EMACS connector	Lightweight publish-subscribe protocol for telemetry data
REST API (HTTPS)	Application Layer	FlexBIT API communication	Used for configuration, command dispatching,

			and analytics data exchange
TLS 1.3	Security	All layers	Ensures encrypted transmission of data

Figure 3 Standardized Communication Protocols

3.4 Integration Technical Description (Demonstrators)

Each demonstrator will maintain local operational control through a fast loop, while the FlexBIT platform will exchange aggregated data and advisory control signals via a slow coordination loop. This ensures interoperability without compromising local autonomy or safety.

3.4.1 German Demonstrator – IFF

The German demonstrator focuses on creating an **industrial energy community** by interconnecting two sites — *Aue Funeral* (tertiary sector) and *aRTE Möbel* (industrial sector).

Both locations include **PV generation** and **battery energy storage systems and electric vehicles charging stations**, which are coordinated to achieve optimal load balancing and renewable utilization. In addition, at the aRTE Möbel demonstrator, the compressed air system and the manufacturing processes can be controlled—directly in the case of the compressed air system and indirectly in the case of the manufacturing processes. In contrast, the Aue Funeral demonstrator offers the possibility to control the temperature of the cooling units, and thus to control the electrical load.

A **real-time SCADA system** exchanges sensor data and sends **Modbus control commands** between both sites to balance generation, consumption, and grid interaction.

All measurements and optimization results are visualized via a **Web-based dashboard**, ensuring transparency and operational insight.

3.4.2 Italian Demonstrator – University of Rome Tor Vergata

The Italian demonstrator is a **Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL)** pilot located at the University of Rome Tor Vergata. It integrates **renewable generation, hydrogen-based storage, battery systems, and controllable loads** to simulate a smart energy community.

The pilot’s main objective is to **maximize renewable self-consumption** and **test advanced energy management algorithms** for hydrogen integration.

The setup includes **PEM fuel cells, metal hydride hydrogen storage, and 10 kWh of battery capacity**.

All devices are connected to a **local SCADA and data acquisition layer** that logs high-frequency measurements and communicates with the **FlexBIT platform via MQTT/REST APIs**.

Predictive analytics and optimization algorithms determine the most efficient use of renewable energy, storage, and grid interaction.

The demonstrator serves as a testbed for multi-vector energy integration, with a specific emphasis on the co-optimization of electrical, hydrogen-based, and battery energy systems. The HiL (Hardware-in-the-Loop) environment enables the evaluation of Virtual Power Plant (VPP) strategies, advanced EMS algorithms, and simulated ancillary services.

3.4.3 Italian Demonstrator – Smart Energy Parking (University of Palermo)

Located at the University of Palermo campus, this demonstrator integrates a **40 kW PV plant, a 46 kWh stationary lithium battery, and V2G (Vehicle-to-Grid) charging infrastructure**.

It aims to evaluate **Demand Response (DR)** capabilities and **Renewable Energy Community (REC)** participation.

The installation includes an intelligent lighting system and communicates with a **central SCADA controller** located in the Smart and Microgrid Laboratory.

The platform enables real-time control of energy storage and EV chargers, supporting **frequency regulation** and **load shifting scenarios**.

3.4.4 Italian Demonstrator – Solar Cooling System in Pantelleria

The Pantelleria demonstrator tests an **innovative solar-powered air-conditioning system (Freescocool 3.0 VMC)** operating with **low-temperature heat sources** (solar, heat pump, waste heat).

It provides controlled ventilation and humidity management while exploiting **thermal inertia for load shifting**.

The system's control panel and monitoring unit communicate with the FlexBIT platform to evaluate how **thermal storage** can contribute to overall grid flexibility.

3.4.5 Maltese Demonstrator – Digital Twin Microgrid

The Maltese demonstrator develops a **digital twin** of a microgrid integrating **PV systems, battery storage, and dynamic loads**.

It employs **Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL)** testing to synchronize real and virtual components for **real-time control and optimization**.

The pilot operates in two stages:

1. **Local Model Development** – offline training and validation using historical data.
2. **Cloud Integration** – migration to cloud-based AI environments (e.g., Azure ML) for predictive modeling and scalability.

The digital twin will later replicate another consortium demonstrator to enable **cross-site data exchange and performance comparison**.

3.4.6 Polish Demonstrator – SME Electrum / Alu-Frost Facility

The Polish demonstrator at **Alu-Frost (near Białystok)** represents an **industrial-scale site integrating PV generation, BESS, EV chargers, and an advanced Energy Management System (EMS)**.

It focuses on implementing **Machine Learning Operations (MLOps)** for real-time optimization of **energy storage performance and production efficiency**.

The infrastructure includes:

- **Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) with EMACS SCADA,**
- **Edge computer with AI accelerator,**
- **IoT sensors and local weather station,**
- **HPC data center for analytics and model training.**

The demonstrator introduces an **ESS Digital Twin** for predictive control and short-term PV forecasting based on sky imagery, enhancing energy autonomy and cost efficiency.

- **Energy Infrastructure Layer:** Physical energy systems including PVs, batteries, hydrogen generators, EV chargers, and controllable loads. Communication via standard industrial protocols (Modbus TCP, IEC 61850, OPC UA).
- **Data Acquisition and Enforcement Layer:** IoT gateways, smart meters, SCADA units, and edge controllers that acquire and normalize data from field devices. This layer supports MQTT, OPC UA, and HTTPS communication with encryption (TLS 1.3).
- **Data Processing Layer:** Responsible for ingestion, time-series storage, and analytical processing (Kafka, RabbitMQ, InfluxDB, PostgreSQL). Incorporates ETL pipelines and AI/ML-based forecasting.
- **Energy Business and Environment Layer:** Manages market participation, flexibility trading, billing, and CO₂ monitoring. Connects with blockchain-based transaction validation (Hyperledger Fabric).
- **Digital Infrastructure Layer:** Handles CI/CD automation, orchestration (Docker, Kubernetes), and cloud/on-premise deployment models.
- **Security and Monitoring Layer:** Implements encryption, authentication (OAuth2/JWT), auditing, and system observability (Prometheus, Grafana, ELK, Loki).

3.4.7 Polish Demonstrator – WUST (Wrocław University of Science and Technology)

At the Wrocław University of Science and Technology, a demonstration laboratory stand will be created to test the regulatory potential of microgrid elements such as photovoltaic inverters, battery energy storage inverters/chargers, and programmable loads. Full identification of the regulatory capabilities of these devices will help identify the scope of microgrid flexibility.

The system includes a 15kW/1500V regenerative DC power supply operating as a hardware photovoltaic array simulator or a battery simulator. The next part of the stand is a laboratory set of a 2.4kWh/48V Li-ion battery energy storage and a laboratory set of controllable active and passive loads.

As part of the FlexBIT project funding from the CET Partnership program, the stand will be equipped with an AC Regenerative Grid Simulator 21kVA/0.4kV. As a result, it will be possible to intentionally hardware-enforce the operating conditions of the microgrid.

Mentioned elements will be integrated into the common laboratory microgrid where different scenarios of the AC supply network condition as well as PV and BES contribution, can be examined.

Laboratory tests will provide boundary characteristics of the regulatory potential of the microgrid components and their response to intentionally created variable conditions in the microgrid. Together with other project partners from Italy and Malta, the results obtained in the WUST test laboratory will contribute to the creation of digital twins of microgrid elements.

Figure 4 Laboratory test bench architecture at WUST

3.5 Demonstrator Integration and Data Flow Example – Hydrogen and Smart Parking (UNIPA and UNIRM2 integration integration, Italy)

The Italian demonstrator at the University of Palermo (UNIPA) consist of a smart energy parking system will be integrated with hydrogen production, storage and utilization demo at the University of Rome Tor Vergata (UNIRM2), acting as a hybrid microgrid node with communication enabled by FlexBIT platform.

The integration combines **local fast control loops** (ensuring autonomous operation of PV generation, hydrogen electrolyzers, and EV charging infrastructure) with a **global advisory loop** coordinated by FlexBIT. This integrated setup enables coordinated decision-making and joint optimization of storage, hydrogen production, and V2G services across distributed infrastructures.

The local controller (based on Raspberry Pi and EMACS-compatible gateway) exchanges monitoring data and control recommendations with the FlexBIT platform through **MQTT/OpenAPI interfaces** over a secured **VPN channel**.

Data collected at the microgrid level includes:

- active/reactive power flow at inverters and fuel cells,
- hydrogen tank pressure and production rate,
- battery state of charge and energy balance,
- EV charging demand and user flexibility levels.

Sampling rate: **every 20 seconds** for monitoring signals;

Local optimization: **every 15 minutes** (energy mix prediction, hydrogen prioritization).

FlexBIT receives aggregated data from the demonstrator and performs **classification of the energy mix** (renewable vs non-renewable contribution) at specific timestamps.

Based on predictive algorithms, the platform returns **advisory recommendations** (slow loop) suggesting when to store or inject energy into the grid, optimizing local prosumer flexibility.

The integration thus enables a **bidirectional information flow**:

- *from local controllers to FlexBIT* → real-time data and flexibility metrics,
- *from FlexBIT to local controllers* → optimization and coordination signals.

Figure X illustrates the data and control flow between the UNIPA demonstrator and the FlexBIT platform, highlighting both the fast (local) and slow (global) control loops.

Use case: classifying (not certifying) the energy mix at specific time

monitoring quantities (at residential level)
 quantity: P in and out from the microgrid
 sampling time: every 20 sec,
 optimization algorithm (local): every 15 minutes
 timestamp: ...

un prosumers can provide energy from batteries, può fornire energia dalla batteria (rinnovabili + fossili nel caso di energia presa dalla rete , dal FV, dalla fuel cell

- H2 può essere generato con diverso mix energetico in ingresso

Different flexibility levels for prosumers (@ ToV)

- Level 0 - No flexibility (they only produce from PV).
- Level 1 - Flexible users because they have PV and a battery.
- Level 2 - Same as Level 1, plus a low-temperature fuel cell.
- Level 3 - Same as Level 2, plus a high-temperature fuel cell, with cogeneration and thermal storage capabilities.

Figure 5 Demonstrator Integration and Data Flow Example

4 IoT Deployment for Real-Time Data Acquisition

4.1 Overview and Objectives

Overview and Objectives

The Internet of Things (IoT) layer of FlexBIT serves as the foundation for **real-time data collection and contextual monitoring** of distributed energy assets across all demonstrators.

It enables unified, continuous, and secure acquisition of electrical, thermal, and environmental data from diverse devices — including PV inverters, hydrogen systems, BESS, EV chargers, and industrial controllers. The main objectives of IoT deployment are to:

- Ensure standardized data acquisition from heterogeneous energy assets.
- Enable edge-level preprocessing and local intelligence for resilience.
- Provide time-synchronized, secure, and high-frequency data streams to the FlexBIT platform.
- Support cross-demonstrator analytics through metadata and semantic tagging.

IoT deployment transforms distributed energy environments into fully observable systems capable of predictive management and flexibility optimization.

4.2 IoT Architecture and Layers

Each FlexBIT demonstrator implements a dedicated IoT setup tailored to its local energy systems, ensuring harmonized and secure data flow toward the FlexBIT cloud platform.

Despite differences in scale and purpose, all pilots share a common IoT architecture composed of field sensors, edge controllers, and communication interfaces (MQTT, Modbus, OPC UA, REST).

This uniform approach enables real-time data acquisition, monitoring, and predictive control across multiple energy domains — including PV, hydrogen, battery, EV charging, and thermal management systems.

All IoT components adhere to standardized cybersecurity measures and data models defined in WP1, ensuring interoperability within the FlexBIT ecosystem.

Demonstrator	Main IoT Devices / Sensors	Measured Parameters	Edge / Control Components	Communication Protocols	Purpose / Data Usage
Germany (IFF)	PV inverters, battery meters, compressor and refrigeration load sensors, temperature and pressure probes	Electric generation and consumption, compressor air pressure, cooling temperature,	Local EMS controller, MODBUS-enabled devices, web-based visualization gateway	Modbus TCP, MQTT, HTTP REST	Real-time monitoring and control of industrial loads; flexibility exploitation, load balancing between two facilities; energy flow optimization
Italy (UNIRM2 – Tor Vergata)	Programmable power supply (PV/Wind simulation), electronic loads, hydrogen flow sensors, temperature sensors, voltage/current probes, smart meters	Electric power, temperature, hydrogen flow/pressure, grid exchange data	HiL controller, SCADA system, time-series database, local optimization engine	MQTT, Modbus, OPC UA, REST API	Testing and optimization of hybrid PV–battery–hydrogen based renewable energy community; real-time control and data logging; integration with FlexBIT analytics
Italy (UNIPA – Smart Parking)	PV system sensors (40 kW), EV chargers (V2G), stationary Li-ion battery (46 kWh), light control system sensors	Electric power generation, battery SOC, EV charge/discharge status, lighting control states	Local controller in Smart & Microgrid Lab (edge gateway), central monitoring server	MQTT, Modbus, V2G API, Ethernet/VPN	Demand Response validation; flexibility tests; real-time participation in REC framework

Demonstrator	Main IoT Devices / Sensors	Measured Parameters	Edge / Control Components	Communication Protocols	Purpose / Data Usage
Italy (Pantelleria – Solar Cooling)	Thermal sensors, humidity and air-quality sensors, flow meters, power meters	Temperature, humidity, airflow rate, power consumption	Local PLC controller, IoT gateway for thermal monitoring	Modbus RTU/TCP, MQTT, REST API	Validation of load-shifting via thermal inertia; integration of Freesco VMC into FlexBIT IoT framework
Malta	PV inverters, battery sensors, load meters, environmental sensors	Voltage, current, load profile, irradiance, temperature	Local IoT gateway, HiL interface, digital twin emulator	MQTT, OPC UA, REST API	Real-time data streaming to Digital Twin and FlexBIT platform; model validation and control simulation
Poland (Electrum / Alu-Frost)	IoT weather station, smart meters, PV sensors, BESS controller sensors, EV charger data acquisition units	Active/reactive power, temperature, irradiance, SOC, EV consumption	EMACS SCADA system, Edge computer (Ubuntu Server), HPC server (data center)	MQTT, Modbus TCP, Delta-Sharing API	AI-driven optimization, ESS Digital Twin updates, predictive PV output estimation, SCADA–FlexBIT synchronization
Poland (WUST)	BESS controller sensors, load meters	Voltage, current, power, SOC	Local controller in microgrid demonstrator.	Modbus TCP, MQTT	Testing of flexibility and integration with FlexBIT monitoring system

Figure 6 IoT Devices and Data Acquisition Setup per Demonstrator

The IoT layer serves as the primary data acquisition backbone of the FlexBIT ecosystem. By standardizing field-level sensing, communication, and data security across demonstrators, it ensures seamless interoperability, enabling the FlexBIT platform to perform predictive analytics, flexibility forecasting, and real-time energy optimization

5 Centralized FlexBIT Platform: Oversee distributed energy resources with real-time monitoring

The FlexBIT architecture represents a modular, scalable platform designed to support digitalized energy management, integration of distributed energy resources (DERs), and advanced energy business services. The system is divided into several logical layers and functional domains, each responsible for specific capabilities within the ecosystem

5.1 FlexBIT Interfaces

This block provides all the user-facing and integration entry points to the platform:

- **Configuration** – Tools for setting up and customizing system parameters, devices, and business rules.
- **FlexBIT API** – Programmatic interface for external systems, allowing data exchange, automation, and integration.
- **Dashboards** – Visualization interfaces for analytics, monitoring, and operational control.
- **Notification and Alerts** – Event-driven messaging and alarms for operators and users.

Figure 7 Flex Bit interface technology

5.2 External Operator Interfaces (Conceptual)

In addition to internal users and demonstrators, the FlexBIT platform is designed to exchange data with external regulated actors operating in the electricity system. These interfaces are addressed at a conceptual level and are not validated within the FlexBIT demonstrators due to the absence of associated partners representing these actors. Nevertheless, they are essential for regulatory completeness and future deployment.

The FlexBIT platform supports **bidirectional communication** with the following external operators:

- Smart Meter Operator
- Energy Supplier
- Distribution System Operator (DSO)
- Market or Incentive Scheme Operator (country-dependent)

All external communications are exposed through the **FlexBIT unified interface and data structures**, ensuring a consistent, secure, and role-based data exchange model independent of national market implementation. Conceptually, these interfaces represent both inbound and outbound communication channels and are depicted on the right-hand side of the FlexBIT architecture under the “FlexBIT unified interface and data structures”, emphasizing data provision from and to external operators.

5.3 Monitoring and Maintenance IT/OT

Effective management of IT and OT systems requires continuous visibility, reliability, and compliance. By integrating logging, monitoring, maintenance, and auditing, organizations can track system health, anticipate issues, and maintain full traceability across software, hardware, and field devices. This section outlines the key strategies and tools supporting these objectives.

5.3.1 Logging - System event registration.

Implements a centralized system for collecting and indexing logs from IT and OT components. Solutions such as ELK Stack, Loki, and OpenTelemetry (OTEL) collectors acquire application logs, platform service events, and data coming from field devices and FlexBIT microservices. OTEL provides standardized instrumentation and exports trace data directly to Grafana Tempo for scalable distributed tracing. Structured, correlated, and searchable telemetry supports troubleshooting, auditing, and post-event analysis, ensuring full traceability and operational insight.

5.3.2 Monitoring - Health, performance, and system state tracking.

A monitoring layer based on **Prometheus** (metrics collection) and **Grafana** (visualization) provides real-time visibility over software services, hardware assets, and energy-related components. Metrics include CPU/memory utilization, microservice latency, device connectivity, and resource availability. Dedicated dashboards enable fast anomaly detection and informed operational decisions.

5.3.3 Maintenance - Tools supporting updates and preventive actions.

Combined insights from logs (ELK/Loki) and metrics (Prometheus) enable predictive and preventive maintenance across IT and OT assets. This supports controlled software updates, microservice deployments, system integrity checks, and proactive interventions on physical devices. Grafana alerts help anticipate failures or performance degradation, improving overall system availability.

5.3.4 Auditing - Compliance checks and historical records of operations.

ELK Stack and Loki ensure secure long-term storage and easy retrieval of operational records, platform interactions, and device-generated events. These capabilities facilitate compliance verification, security review, incident assessment, and reporting required by regulators or certification frameworks.

Figure 8 Monitoring and Maintenance IT/OT

5.4 Security

The security layer provides foundational cybersecurity and access control mechanisms that protect data, services, and interactions within the FlexBIT platform. These mechanisms are designed to operate consistently across components while supporting scalability and interoperability.

Privacy mechanisms protect personal, sensitive, and operational information by enforcing data minimisation principles, role- and purpose-based access control, and preventing unauthorised exposure. Privacy is particularly important in multi-stakeholder environments spanning organisational and administrative boundaries. Given that the energy domain is a characteristic example of such an environment, the FlexBIT platform supports regulatory compliance to maintain user trust.

Encryption is used to protect communications and store information from unauthorised access, interception, and tampering. Securing data in transit supports confidential and integrity-protected interactions between platform components, while encryption at rest mitigates the impact of data breaches and infrastructure compromises.

Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting (AAA) mechanisms provide identity management, access control, and usage monitoring. Authentication verifies the identities of users, services, and devices, while authorization enforces fine-grained access policies based on assigned roles and permissions. Accounting supports auditing and monitoring, enabling accountability and compliance in multi-tenant environments.

Together, these mechanisms ensure the secure and trustworthy operation of the FlexBIT platform.

5.5 Energy Business & Environment

Supports commercial and regulatory processes:

- **Energy Market Integration** – Participation in electricity markets and trading mechanisms.
- **Billing** – Automated calculations, invoicing, and settlements.
- **Energy Services** – Value-added services for customers and operators.

- **Regulation Compliance** – Ensures adherence to legal and environmental requirements.
 - **CO₂ Emissions** – Tracking and reporting of carbon footprint.
- Interaction with External Operators** - The Energy Business & Environment layer acts as the mediation and coordination layer between the FlexBIT platform and external regulated actors. It abstracts national regulatory differences and enables consistent interaction with unbundled or bundled market structures.

In unbundled electricity markets (e.g., Germany), the following roles are considered as separate entities:

- Smart Meter Operator
- Energy Supplier
- Distribution System Operator

In other national contexts, one or more of these roles may be operated by a single organization. FlexBIT supports this variability through role-based interface mapping, allowing one entity to implement multiple roles while preserving functional separation at the platform level.

This layer manages the aggregation, validation, and preparation of energy and flexibility data exchanged with external operators for settlement, billing, grid operation, and regulatory reporting.

5.6 FlexBIT Energy Management

Core functional layer responsible for managing energy assets:

5.6.1 VPP Controller – Controls Virtual Power Plant operations.

In **Poland**, the demonstrators will focus on **residential, tertiary, and industrial energy systems**, representing an **energy community at regional scale**. Within this framework, the **manufacturing facility of AluFrost** and the **Headquarters Building of Electrum** will operate as an **active Virtual Power Plant (VPP)**, aggregating distributed energy resources to provide **flexibility services** to the **local system operator**.

These sites will showcase coordinated control of generation, storage, and flexible demand, demonstrating how heterogeneous assets can be orchestrated to support grid stability, optimize local energy flows, and enable market-oriented flexibility at community level.

5.6.2 Optimization Engine – Computes optimal schedules and strategies

The Optimization Engine is a core intelligence module designed to orchestrate the coordinated use of energy assets across residential, tertiary, and industrial environments. Its primary objective is to enable smart, dynamic control by identifying optimal operation schedules that balance energy demand, availability of renewables, storage capacity, and market opportunities. By leveraging predictive models and scenario analysis, the engine enhances system-wide energy efficiency and flexibility.

Key impacts and objectives include:

- **Maximizing renewable energy self-consumption** by aligning energy use with generation forecasts.
- **Minimizing operational costs** through time- and price-sensitive scheduling.
- **Reducing grid stress** by shifting or shaving peak loads.
- **Supporting Net-Zero Energy objectives** by harmonizing local production, storage, and consumption.
- **Enabling participation in flexibility markets** (e.g., demand response, ancillary services).

Integrated within the FlexBIT architecture, the Optimization Engine acts as the decision-making hub that transforms raw data into actionable control strategies, ensuring resilient and economically optimized energy operations.

5.6.3 Energy storage (battery mgt, thermal, hydrogen and compressed air)

Energy storage systems such as batteries, thermal storage, compressed air, and hydrogen are key components for exploiting the flexibility required to maximize energy self-consumption. However, their operation and control can lead to energy inefficiencies in the range of 20–40%. For this reason, the control hierarchy adopted in each demonstrator does not consider energy storage units as the first option when other flexibility measures are available.

To operate energy storage units in the most effective way, parameters such as state of charge, state of health, charging and discharging power, temperature, and pressure are either directly monitored in real time (where possible) or indirectly estimated through validated algorithms.

5.6.4 Forecasting – Predicts energy production, demand, and prices.

Provides predictive capabilities for **PV generation** (1-15 minute horizons) and **load demand** (short-, medium-, and long-term) to support energy management within the FlexBIT platform. The module combines **deep learning** and **machine learning** approaches, utilizing reference datasets (SKIPP'D, Almería) and FlexBIT demonstrator data for model development and validation. Integration with **EMACS** via **REST API** endpoints is planned to support the advisory control loop and cross-demonstrator analytics.

5.6.5 Energy Community – Enables local energy sharing models.

The energy community function enables electricity sharing among community members through configurable settlement registration rules tailored to each demonstrator. Each registration defines:

- Metering Points: Energy meters included in the settlement calculation
- Time Resolution: Measurement intervals (15 minutes, 30 minutes, or 1 hour)
- Energy Flow Classification:
 - Peer-to-peer sharing among community members,
 - Net balancing between the community and external supplier,
 - Flexibility services provided to the system operator (Ancillary Services) such as demand response

In addition to it, the energy community function shares information with smart meter operators, energy supplier and distributed system operator. The sharing of information is bidirectional. It provides data for the module “Energy Business & Environment” of the FlexBIT platform.

5.6.6 Ancillary Services – Supports frequency regulation, reserves, etc.

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The Ancillary Services function enables FlexBIT to support **grid stability and reliability** by exploiting the flexibility of aggregated distributed energy resources (DERs). Flexible assets such as batteries, EVs (V2G), and controllable loads are coordinated to provide system services beyond energy trading. FlexBIT conceptually supports:

- **Frequency regulation** through fast active power modulation,
- **Operating reserves** (upward and downward) from storage and flexible demand,
- **Demand Response (DR)** for peak shaving and congestion management
- **Reactive power and voltage support**, where enabled by inverter capabilities and regulation Ancillary services are implemented using the **two-loop control architecture**:
 - a **local fast loop** ensuring real-time, safe execution by SCADA/EMS systems,
 - a **central advisory loop** where FlexBIT aggregates flexibility and issues coordination signals.

High-resolution metering and operational data enable **verification, settlement, and regulatory reporting**, with optional blockchain-based traceability. Within energy communities, flexibility is first optimized locally and can subsequently be offered to external operators (e.g., DSOs) under applicable regulatory frameworks.

5.7 FlexBIT Smart Contracts

This component is central to the digitalization and blockchain strategy, leveraging Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) to establish a decentralized, immutable infrastructure for the transparent management of energy communities and flexibility markets. By implementing programmable Smart Contracts in Solidity, FlexBIT automates complex operational logic and financial settlements, ensuring non-repudiation and security through Hyperledger Besu's permissioned framework.

5.7.1 Automated Transaction Settlement

Objective: To facilitate trustless financial and operational reconciliation within Energy Communities and local flexibility markets.

Mechanism: Smart contracts automatically execute settlements based on verified meter data and agreed-upon price signals. When a residential or industrial partner provides a flexibility service (e.g., discharging an electrochemical battery or adjusting thermal load), the contract autonomously triggers the corresponding value transfer or credit assignment immediately, thereby streamlining the process and significantly increasing the economic attractiveness of flexibility supply. This mechanism is crucial for enabling buildings to participate as active energy systems.

5.7.2 Traceability of Energetic Sustainability

Objective: To certify the verifiable "green" origin of energy used in processes and track shared flexibility services across the system.

Mechanism: FlexBIT utilizes the Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) to establish an immutable audit trail that digitally links renewable energy generation (RES) directly to specific consumption events. This supports the core project goal of tracking the energetic sustainability of all tertiary and industrial processes within the consortium. This process creates a digital "product passport" verified by blockchain, providing irrefutable evidence of the use of green energy in manufactured items or services. The mechanism is a direct application of the Distributed Approaches methodology, guaranteeing transparency and supporting future reporting requirements on carbon footprint.

5.7.3 Operational Logic and Privacy

Objective: To enforce grid constraints and community rules through secure, automated validation while maintaining data privacy.

Mechanism:

- **Trustless Validation:** Operational logic for validating flexibility activation (e.g., did the system successfully reduce load when requested?) is written into the Smart Contract. This ensures that neither the Distributed System Operator (DSO) nor the service provider can dispute the fulfillment of a service order, securing shared flexibility of services.
- **Decentralized Control:** This layer supports the peer-to-peer interactions necessary for the operation of small-scale energy communities. It also incorporates privacy-preserving computation to respect user data confidentiality while allowing validated energy transactions within the community context.
- **DER Management:** Contracts manage the registration and ongoing participation of individual Points of Delivery (PODs). Each POD's operational profile is automatically checked against technical and regulatory

rules. Once approved, participation is tracked and recorded immutably to ensure compliance with community rules and facilitate automated settlements.

Figure 9 FlexBIT Smart Contracts: DLT-Base Energy Community Management

5.8 FlexBIT Blockchain

FlexBIT will use a distributed ledger layer enabling transparency, immutability, and trust in data exchange across the multi-vector energy landscape.

5.8.1 Permissioned Infrastructure and BFT Governance

FlexBIT has selected Hyperledger Besu as the core blockchain client, a decision driven by its full compatibility with the European Blockchain Service Infrastructure (EBSI) and the extensive prior implementation experience of the consortium partners. The network utilizes an enterprise-grade permissioned architecture implementing Byzantine Fault Tolerant (BFT) consensus protocols—specifically QBFT or IBFT 2.0—to achieve immediate transaction finality and prevent chain forks. This governance structure ensures that validator sets participate in a round-based process to finalize blocks, maintaining high operational reliability even if some participants are adversarial. For the network to maintain consensus and avoid stalling, the number of active validators must satisfy the Byzantine condition:

$$N \geq 3f + 1$$

Where f is the number of tolerated faulty nodes.

5.8.2 Data Integrity and Account-Based Permissioning

A primary advantage of the chosen infrastructure is the integration of the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM), which allows the platform to leverage the mature Ethereum development ecosystem while maintaining a secure, permissioned environment. Rather than relying on external privacy-management middleware, FlexBIT

handles data protection through native, granular network-level permissioning and a hybrid storage model. By utilizing Hyperledger Besu's account and node permissioning features, the system ensures that only authorized entities can interact with the network or propose state changes. Sensitive telemetry data remains in secure off-chain databases, while only the resulting cryptographic hashes are committed to the ledger serving as a tamper-proof "Source of Truth" for auditing. This approach safeguards the system from cyber threats by ensuring that only authenticated participants can verify state transitions without exposing raw industrial performance metrics.

5.8.3 Automated Settlement and Traceability

The system leverages automated smart contracts, developed in Solidity for EVM-compatible execution, to manage Peer-to-Peer (P2P) trade settlements and enforce energy community rules in a trustless manner. These contracts govern the complex logic of local energy distributor and energy supply operator across residential, tertiary, and industrial sectors, providing a transparent framework for the automated financial reconciliation of flexibility services and cross-sectoral energy balancing. By facilitating both horizontal exchanges within the same community and vertical exchanges among neighboring communities, the platform ensures that remuneration for provided flexibility capacity is shared transparently among participants based on verified a-posteriori contributions.

The platform enables the immutable verification of energy flows across the distribution network, recording production metrics from diverse renewable sources and storage technologies directly to the ledger. By leveraging this tamper-proof record, the system provides high-fidelity traceability of renewable energy origin and consumption patterns, ensuring compliance with European sustainability directives without manual intervention. By reconciling these multi-vector energy flows against verified meter data, the platform reduces administrative barriers and promotes active participation in decarbonization efforts across all transnational pilot sites.

Primary Characteristics of the Distributed Ledger Layer

- **EBSI-Aligned Architecture:** Utilizes Hyperledger Besu to ensure compatibility and interoperability with European public service infrastructures.
- **QBFT Consensus Protocol:** Implements an enterprise-grade protocol to provide immediate finality and high-throughput for energy transactions.
- **EVM-Compatible Smart Contracts:** Leverages Solidity-based logic for the automated and transparent execution of energy sharing and flexibility market rules.
- **Network-Level Access Control:** Strict permissioning schemes ensure only authorized consortium partners can participate in the validation and governance of the ledger.
- **Hybrid Integrity Model:** Protects sensitive data by combining off-chain storage with on-chain cryptographic hashing to maintain a permanent audit trail.
- **Green Origin Traceability:** Enables the immutable verification of renewable energy contributions via blockchain-verified sustainability passports.

5.9 Data Acquisition and Enforcement

The **Data Acquisition and Enforcement** layer connects physical energy assets with the FlexBIT platform by ensuring **reliable data collection and secure execution of control signals**. It provides the trusted data foundation required for monitoring, optimization, and flexibility management.

Data are collected from **smart meters, IoT devices, and local SCADA/EMS systems** and aggregated through edge gateways. Measurements include power flows, energy consumption, storage states, and operational

status of DERs. Data are validated, time-synchronized, and securely transmitted to the FlexBIT platform using standardized protocols (MQTT, OPC UA, REST over TLS).

The enforcement function translates FlexBIT **advisory control signals** into locally executable actions, while preserving **local autonomy, safety, and fail-safe operation**. Real-time control remains at the local level, ensuring that FlexBIT coordination does not interfere with critical system functions.

This layer enables trustworthy analytics, verification of flexibility and ancillary services, and compliant data exchange with external operators.

Figure 10 Data Acquisitions and Enforcement

5.9.1 Aggregators and Bidirectional Control Flow

The Platform receives data through the DataAggregators installed in each community member’s network. Inside the DataAggregator software, all the devices that have to be monitored or controlled need to be configured by selecting their compatible protocol (MQTT, HTTP, MODBUS TCP, etc.), their IP/Port, and additional connection properties, for example, in the case of MODBUS TCP, all the registers with corresponding function code and datatype for all the individual signals. After a DataAggregator is deployed and configured, the software connects to all of the Energy Devices inside the corresponding network and sends the sensor readings through an MQTT broker to the Flexbit Platform. The Flexbit Platform then calculates, based on the operation presets (defined at the beginning by the corresponding CommunityOperator via an editor inside the Flexbit Platform), control commands for each FlexibleDevice to achieve the highest possible use of volatile energy production. Input for the operation presets are weather predictions (and any other configured/integrated REST API service), load predictions, sensor readings, and/or static user values, which all can be logically connected via basic boolean and/or arithmetic operations. Afterwards, the calculated output (control commands) will be sent via the same MQTT broker back to the DataAggregator in charge and from there to the target device.

5.10 Communication

5.10.1 Protocols

FlexBIT adopts a streamlined communication model that cleanly separates local device interaction from platform-level data exchange. Within each demonstrator, devices communicate with either a local or cloud-based adapter through lightweight or domain-specific protocols such as MQTT, Modbus, or other custom field interfaces. This supports integration with heterogeneous equipment without requiring changes to existing systems. Independent of adapter placement, all communication from the adapter to the FlexBIT platform is standardized through REST APIs, ensuring a consistent, secure, and maintainable interface for all demonstrators.

5.10.2 Networks

The networking architecture ensures secure connectivity between demonstrators, adapters, and the central FlexBIT platform.

The system can operate in two modes depending on the deployment context:

- VPN-secured communication is used when demonstrators prefer a dedicated encrypted tunnel between local systems and the platform.
- Public REST API access with strong authentication, enabling secure communication without requiring a VPN. API keys, token-based authentication, and HTTPS encryption provide protection even when endpoints are publicly reachable.
- Isolated server networks / VLAN segmentation to separate internal services and restrict access to defined API interfaces.
- Firewall-controlled ingress points ensuring that only authenticated REST traffic can access platform services.

This dual approach provides flexibility: a VPN is supported when desired but not required, as secure API-based communication is sufficient.

5.10.3 IoT Gateways

IoT gateways form the operational bridge between field devices and the FlexBIT platform.

They provide:

- Protocol Translation - Converting MQTT, Modbus, and other field-level protocols into the platform's unified data model.
- Data Aggregation - Collecting and structuring data from sensors, meters, and controllers.
- Edge Processing - Applying filtering, buffering, or lightweight computation to reduce bandwidth and improve responsiveness.
- Secure Data Forwarding - Sending data to the platform exclusively via encrypted REST API requests, either through a VPN or directly over public networks when API authentication is in place.

By supporting local and cloud-based adapters and flexible connection modes, gateways ensure scalable, secure, and interoperable connectivity across all FlexBIT demonstrators.

Figure 11 Communication Framework: Device&System Connectivity

5.10.4 External Communication Channels

In addition to internal device and demonstrator communication, the FlexBIT platform conceptually supports outbound and inbound communication with external operators via the unified interface and data structures. These channels are depicted on the right-hand side of the architecture under the FlexBIT unified interface and data structures and include:

- Data exchange with Smart Meter Operators for certified metering and settlement support
- Data exchange with Energy Suppliers for billing, residual energy balancing, and tariff application
- Data exchange with Distribution System Operators for grid constraints, flexibility provision, and operational coordination
- Data exchange with Market or Incentive Scheme Operators for incentive claims related to shared energy and flexibility services (e.g., renewable energy communities in Italy)

These communication channels are defined at an architectural level and are intended to support future regulatory integration.

5.11 Data Processing

Data processing layer represents the backbone of the platform, ingesting and storing data, enabling further analytics and processing. This layer connects data sources, encapsulated in the data acquisition and enforcement layer, with data consumers, such as dashboards, AI models, management systems and more. In the context of the platform, data processing layer needs to operate on multiple scales and granularities, allowing for real-time data ingestion and historical data access.

Data ingestion is impacted by the presence of heterogeneous data sources, e.g., sensors, SCADA, smart meters, etc. This further characterises data with varying update frequencies, formats, and volumes. This motivates the use of Apache Kafka and RabbitMQ for data ingestion and queueing.

Apache Kafka is chosen to support high-throughput, distributed data ingestion by enabling scalable and durable event streaming. It decouples data producers from downstream consumers, allowing data to be ingested asynchronously and processed independently at different rates. It provides built-in buffering and

persistence, supporting reliable data delivery under varying workloads and temporary failures. Thus, Kafka is well-suited for continuous data streams, commonly seen in energy management scenarios.

RabbitMQ enables reliable and controlled asynchronous communication between system components. It supports fine-grained routing, acknowledgments, and retry mechanisms, which are essential for handling ingestion workflows that require acknowledged delivery and processing control. By buffering messages and applying back-pressure, RabbitMQ prevents overload of downstream services and improves overall system robustness.

Kafka and RabbitMQ provide complementary ingestion and queueing capabilities, allowing FlexBIT system to efficiently handle both high-volume data streams and complex data-driven workflows.

As the data is ingested and processed continuously, the storage capabilities of the FlexBIT platform need to be respectively diverse, supporting all the nuanced data usage scenarios. Thus, FlexBIT supports multiple databases, depending on their target tasks supported:

1. Relational database (e.g., PostgreSQL) — stores structured, general-purpose data requiring strong consistency guarantees, well-defined schemas, and support for complex queries and transactional operations.
2. NoSQL database (e.g., MongoDB) — manages unstructured or semi-structured data, providing flexible data models and horizontal scalability suitable for heterogeneous and evolving data sources.
3. Time-series database (e.g., InfluxDB) — is used for time-series data collection and storage, supporting efficient handling of high-frequency, timestamped data and supporting temporal queries and aggregations.

Data access is further supported by Redis — an in-memory cache that provides low-latency access to frequently accessed data and intermediate results, reducing load on persistent storage and improving overall system responsiveness.

Together, these storage technologies support diverse data characteristics and access patterns, enabling efficient, scalable, and reliable data management across FlexBIT platform.

Analytics within this data processing layer focuses on transforming ingested data into structured insights and interpretable representations that support monitoring, assessment, and downstream intelligence components. This includes such activities as data aggregation, statistical analysis, trend extraction, anomaly detection, and metrics computation.

As a result, the ingested and stored data becomes easily available for other modules of the platform, responsible for high-level data analytics, visualization, and AI pipelines.

Figure 12 Data processing

5.12 Digital Infrastructure

The runtime environment provides the foundational execution layer for the entire platform, ensuring that all services, applications, and analytics components operate reliably, consistently, and at scale. It integrates several core technologies that together enable standardized development, resilient operations, and efficient deployment processes across all demonstrators.

5.12.1 PaaS - Platform-as-a-Service

The PaaS layer offers a fully managed environment for application development and deployment. By abstracting the underlying hardware and operating system configurations, it provides uniform tooling, standardized runtime components, and managed services that simplify the entire software lifecycle. This enables development teams to concentrate on energy analytics, business logic, and user-facing services without having to maintain infrastructure or manage system-level dependencies.

5.12.2 Containers (Docker)

Containers encapsulate applications and microservices into lightweight and portable execution units. Each container holds everything required for consistent operation, including runtime libraries and dependencies. This ensures stable behavior across local development, testing facilities, and cloud or on-premises deployments in multiple countries. Containers also improve scalability by allowing services to be rapidly replicated or adjusted in response to workload fluctuations.

5.12.3 Orchestration (Kubernetes)

Kubernetes manages the deployment and lifecycle of containerized applications, ensuring continuous availability and resilience. It automates workload scheduling, monitors system health, distributes traffic, and restarts failed components without manual intervention. This orchestration capability is essential for platforms operating across geographically distributed demonstrators, where uptime, fault tolerance, and efficient resource allocation are critical requirements.

5.12.4 CI/CD - Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment

CI/CD pipelines provide automated mechanisms for integrating code changes, running tests, validating compliance, and deploying software updates. These pipelines support faster development cycles, reduce manual configuration errors, and increase release predictability. For a platform like FlexBIT, CI/CD ensures that analytics models, services, and backend components can evolve rapidly while maintaining consistency and quality across all deployments.

Key points:

- Consistent and repeatable deployments
- Automated quality checks throughout the pipeline

5.13 Energy Infrastructure

The Energy Infrastructure Layer comprises the physical energy systems that generate, store, and consume energy within the FlexBIT ecosystem. It constitutes the material foundation upon which digital control, monitoring, optimization, and forecasting services operate.

The infrastructure includes the following components:

- **Renewable generation systems** such as photovoltaic installations, micro-wind generation, hybrid systems, fuel cells and thermal recovery units;
- **Energy storage technologies**, including electrochemical batteries (Li-ion, LFP, flow), thermal storage units, and hydrogen-based storage with electrolyzers and compressed air systems;
- **Electric mobility assets**, including EV charging stations and V2G-enabled infrastructures that act as flexible

resources;

– **Controllable loads**, such as heat pumps, HVAC systems, industrial processes, cooling systems and smart lighting installations;

– **Measurement and protection equipment** including smart meters, power quality sensors, inverters, and PLCs.

All components are integrated through standard industrial communication protocols (Modbus TCP, OPC UA, IEC 61850) and interface with the local Edge Gateway, which manages data synchronization, buffering, and command execution.

The Energy Infrastructure Layer fulfills three principal functions:

1. supporting **multi-vector energy optimization** across electrical, thermal, and hydrogen systems;
2. enabling **local flexibility provision** through real-time control executed in the fast loop, coordinated with the FlexBIT advisory loop;
3. ensuring **high-resolution measurability and traceability** of energy flows and KPIs through advanced sensing and telemetry systems.

This layer, while common in conceptual structure across all demonstrators, is customized to local configurations and operational requirements. It provides the basis for digital modelling, Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL) and Software-in-the-Loop (SiL) simulations, and the validation of advanced control strategies developed in WP2–WP4.

6 Data Analytics Platform: Enable predictive analysis and optimization of energy flows

The **Data Analytics Platform** represents the intelligence layer of the FlexBIT ecosystem, enabling data-driven insights, predictive forecasting, and optimization of energy flows across distributed demonstrators. This layer leverages real-time data collected from IoT sensors, EMACS SCADA systems, and smart meters to perform advanced analyses that support operational and strategic decision-making.

6.1 System Overview

The platform is designed as a modular analytical environment, combining:

- **Data ingestion and preprocessing pipelines,**
- **AI/ML-based forecasting models** for solar production and load demand,
- **Optimization and decision-support modules,**
- **Visualization of dashboards and reporting interfaces.**

Data streams from distributed assets—PV, wind, fuel cells, hydrogen storage, EV chargers, and building loads—are synchronized via the **IoT Data Hub** and the **centralized SCADA (EMACS)**. This ensures consistent, time-aligned datasets for model training and real-time inference.

6.2 Predictive Forecasting Framework

Within **WP2**, two primary forecasting domains have been developed and integrated into the analytics platform

6.2.1 Short-term Solar Forecasting

Short-term solar forecasting is a critical component of the FlexBIT analytics platform, enabling predictive control and optimization of photovoltaic generation across distributed demonstrators. Accurate forecasts at minute-level resolution support real-time decision-making for battery dispatch, demand response activation, and grid flexibility services. Within the FlexBIT architecture, the forecasting module is designed to support the advisory (slow) control loop by providing actionable predictions that inform energy management strategies.

Objectives and Data Requirements

The forecasting module is being developed to provide predictions of PV generation with horizons ranging from 1 to 15 minutes. This temporal granularity aligns with the operational requirements of the FlexBIT platform for storage optimization and flexibility service provision.

The forecasting framework is being designed around high-frequency data streams with 1-minute temporal resolution. Two reference datasets are being considered for model development and benchmarking:

- **SKIPP'D (Stanford, USA)** – sky images (2048×2048 px) with corresponding PV power output (kW) or benchmark (64×64 px);
- **Almería (Spain)** – sky images (2048×2048 px) with Short Wave Downward Radiation (SWD, W/m²) measurements.

The 15-minute ahead forecasting model presented in the SKIPP'D dataset publication serves as the reference baseline for performance comparison. Cross-dataset experiments require harmonization of heterogeneous measurements, with scaling approaches such as quantile and robust scaling under consideration. For the Polish demonstrator at Alu-Frost, integration of all-sky camera infrastructure is being planned to enable on-site validation.

Model Architectures Under Consideration

Two parallel forecasting architectures are being considered to assess the contribution of sky imagery to prediction accuracy:

Figure 12 PV/SWD Forecasting Architectures

Architecture A: Image-based Forecasting – combines deep learning approaches (CNN for spatial feature extraction, LSTM or Liquid Neural Networks for temporal modeling) processing sky image sequences together with historical PV/SWD values and astronomical features (sun zenith and azimuth angles) derived from timestamps. It is possible that instead of raw sky images, pre-extracted features from the Stanford benchmark will be utilized.

Architecture B: Feature-based Forecasting – utilizes only numerical features including historical PV/SWD values, astronomical features, and time encodings. Various machine learning algorithms are being considered, including gradient boosting methods (XGBoost, LightGBM), random forests, and ensemble techniques. This comparative approach enables assessment of whether the additional complexity of image-based methods is justified by improved forecasting performance.

Evaluation Framework

Model performance evaluation is being designed around Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) as the primary metric. Additional evaluation dimensions under consideration include Clear Sky Index analysis, variance of recent measurements, and cross-location generalization testing.

6.2.2 Load Forecasting and Energy Demand Prediction

Complementary to short-term solar forecasting, load forecasting capabilities are being developed to support energy management optimization across FlexBIT demonstrators. This work is being conducted by Wrocław University of Science and Technology (WUST), Systems Research Institute Polish Academy of Sciences (SRI PAS), and Università degli Studi di Palermo (UniPa).

Forecasting Horizons Under Consideration

Different forecasting horizons are being considered to address various operational needs:

- Short-term (minutes–hours) – for real-time control and operational dispatch;
- Medium-term (days–weeks) – for scheduling and resource optimization;
- Long-term (months–years) – for investment and infrastructure planning.

Model performance evaluation across different time horizons, seasonal conditions, and regional characteristics is being planned to ensure forecasting reliability under diverse operational scenarios.

Model Architectures

Various deep learning architectures are being considered, including LSTM, GRU, CNN-LSTM, LSTM AutoEncoder, and Transformer-based networks. The selection of appropriate architecture will depend on the specific forecasting horizon and demonstrator requirements.

Data Sources and Preprocessing

The forecasting framework is being designed around high-frequency data streams with 1-minute temporal resolution identified as optimal. Historical time series data from FlexBIT demonstrators are being utilized for model development, including data from arteMöbel (Germany) and Alu-Frost (Poland). Data quality criteria emphasize high completeness, with preference for original measurements. Data preprocessing pipelines under development include data cleaning, gap filling, normalization, resampling, and time series sequence generation.

6.3 Platform Integration and Data Flow

The **Data Analytics Platform** is being designed to interface with core FlexBIT components:

- **EMACS SQL** and time server, providing historical and live data;
- **IoT Data Hub**, for near real-time streams via MQTT;
- **SCADA** services, for contextual and metadata enrichment;
- **FlexBIT blockchain** layer, for recording forecasting results and decisions for traceability.

The data pipeline is being designed to ensure bidirectional flow:

1. **Incoming data** from field assets → preprocessing and normalization;
2. **Model inference** → generation of predicted load, production, and irradiance curves;
3. **Optimization module** → computation of control recommendations (e.g., storage dispatch, demand response);
4. **Publishing results** → back to EMACS/SCADA for visualization and operator support.

Forecasting models (both solar and load) will be made available through **REST API endpoints**, enabling seamless integration with other platform modules. **Edge deployment** capabilities are being considered to enable low-latency inference at demonstrator sites, reducing data transfer requirements and supporting near real-time forecasting operations. Collaborative development is conducted via shared **GitHub** repositories to ensure alignment between partners.

6.4 Tools and Environment

Layer	Technology / Tool	Description
Data processing	Python, Pandas, NumPy, Scikit-learn	Cleaning, feature extraction, normalization
Deep learning	PyTorch, TensorFlow	Training and inference of forecasting models

Layer	Technology / Tool	Description
Visualization	Streamlit, Matplotlib, SQL Reporting Services	Web dashboards for operators
Collaboration	GitHub, Jupyter/Colab	Shared development of forecasting algorithms
Deployment	REST API, Docker	Integration of model services into FlexBIT environment

Figure 13 Tools and Environment

6.5 Functional Benefits

The integration of predictive analytics enables:

- **Forecasting of renewable generation and consumption patterns** with minute-level granularity;
- **Optimization of energy flows** between production, storage, and demand;
- **Dynamic control strategies** for the EMACS supervisory system;
- **Cross-demonstrator analysis** for benchmarking and energy sharing scenarios;
- **Improved stability and self-consumption** of renewable-based microgrids.
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6.6 Conclusion

The Data Analytics Platform within FlexBIT is being developed to merge advanced forecasting capabilities with operational control and energy optimization. By combining **short-term PV prediction, load forecasting, and AI-based decision models**, the platform is designed to transform raw SCADA and IoT data into actionable intelligence. It forms the analytical backbone of FlexBIT, bridging real-time monitoring with predictive control and long-term system optimization. The Blueprint provides a coherent and scalable architectural foundation for the implementation of all technical Work Packages. It enables systematic comparison and benchmarking across demonstrators and establishes common rules for data governance, interoperability, and cybersecurity. By defining unified control principles, communication frameworks, and data models, it ensures that the developments in WP2–WP5 remain aligned and collectively contribute to the realization of a distributed, interoperable, and flexible multi-vector energy platform.

7 Conceptual Interfaces with External Energy Operators

External Operator Communication Interfaces (Conceptual)

In addition to internal coordination between demonstrators and the FlexBIT platform, an energy community operating under European regulatory frameworks requires structured communication with external market and grid actors. While these interfaces cannot be technically validated within the FlexBIT project due to the absence of associated partners, they are conceptually essential and are therefore addressed at an architectural level.

From a regulatory perspective—particularly considering the German legal framework and comparable European models—the FlexBIT platform is designed to conceptually support bidirectional data exchange with the following actors:

- Smart Meter Operator (SMO)

The platform shall be capable of receiving validated metering data (energy consumption, injection, time-stamped measurements) from certified smart metering systems. Conceptually, FlexBIT may also provide aggregated flexibility or consumption information required for settlement, verification, or regulatory reporting.

- Energy Supplier (where external)

In cases where electricity supply is managed by an external entity, FlexBIT should exchange aggregated consumption, production, and flexibility activation data. This supports billing, balancing responsibility, and transparency of energy community operations.

- Distribution System Operator (DSO)

FlexBIT conceptually supports interfaces for sharing grid-relevant information with DSOs, including aggregated load profiles, flexibility availability, activation status, and compliance with grid constraints. Conversely, DSOs may provide congestion signals, grid status indicators, or flexibility requests.

- Market Operator

For specific energy community configurations (e.g., participation in local flexibility markets or ancillary services), FlexBIT may conceptually interface with market operators to exchange bids, activation confirmations, and settlement data.

Depending on national unbundling rules, a single entity may fulfill multiple roles (e.g., SMO, DSO, and Supplier). The FlexBIT architecture therefore treats these actors as logical roles rather than fixed organizational entities.

All external interfaces are considered at a conceptual level only and are assumed to rely on standardized, secure communication mechanisms (e.g., REST APIs, standardized market messages, certified data hubs) in compliance with national regulations. Their inclusion in the architecture ensures regulatory completeness, future scalability, and alignment with real-world energy community deployment conditions.